

**Workshop on Artificial Intelligence Techniques for the Optimization of
Electric Power Distribution Systems
5 May 2022, Porto, Portugal**

**Multi-Objective Optimization for the Optimal Subtransmission
Switching with Losses and Reliability Costs**

**Sergio Zambrano-Asanza^{1,2}/ Tatianac Proano Barros³/ Stalinc Banegas Dutan³/
Edwinb Lema Guaman³/ John Fredy Franco¹**

1- Department of Electrical Engineering, São Paulo State University – UNESP, Ilha Solteira, SP, Brazil

2- Department of Planning, CENTROSUR Electric Distribution Utility, Cuenca, Ecuador.

3- School of Electrical Engineering, University of Cuenca, Cuenca, Ecuador

Abstract:

The growth of subtransmission network aims at satisfying load growth, maintaining a contingency level, and providing a high quality and reliable electricity service. Utilities direct the investments to reinforce this system and thus a meshed network with multiple-point feeding to the transmission system arises. At this point, an efficient alternative to achieve these objectives is to carry out a diagnosis of the network architecture and, taking advantage of the switching capability, to plan the switching of the subtransmission lines. An optimal subtransmission switching approach is proposed based on constrained multi-objective optimization that deals with energy losses and reliability, in addition to using information on the characteristics of loads and generation. A simulation-based optimization framework is constructed using the non-dominated genetic classification algorithm NSGA-II in the optimization phase and reliability assessment during simulation phase. As a result, a set of non-dominated solutions approximating the Pareto front is obtained, which allows the planner to make decisions based on their priorities and needs. The performance of the proposal is assessed with a real subtransmission system of an Ecuadorian power utility. This approach to the operational planning of a meshed subtransmission network constitutes a powerful decision-making tool that could be adopted by distribution utilities.

Related References:

Zambrano-Asanza, Sergio and Proano Barros, Tatiana and Banegas Dutan, Stalin and Lema Guaman, Edwin and Franco, John Fredy, Optimal Subtransmission Switching Planning Using a Reliability Simulation-Based Multi-Objective Optimization Model. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3978366> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3978366>